

Factors Shaping Reading Strategy Use among English Language Learners in Pakistan: A Systematic Review

Noor-e-Sahar¹, Shagufta Yasmeen², Sumra Peeran*³, Huma Safdar⁴

¹Senior Lecturer, Academic Coordinator, Ziauddin University, Karachi

²Senior Lecturer, Humanities and Social Sciences, Bahria University. Karachi Campus

³Academics and Operations Manager, UK Examination Board, Learning Resource Network LRN, UK

⁴PhD Scholar, Department of Education, Institute of Business Management, Karachi

nooresahar03@gmail.com¹, shagufta.bukc@bahria.edu.pk², sumra.peeran@lrnglobal.org³
huma.Safdar33@gmail.com⁴

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords

English Reading Strategies;
English As A Second
Language; Systematic
Review; Pakistani Context;
Reading Proficiency;
Metacognitive Awareness

Article History

Received on 22 Nov 2025

Accepted on 30 Dec 2025

Published on 17 Jan 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Sumra Peeran

Academics and Operations
Manager, UK Examination
Board, Learning Resource
Network LRN, UK
sumra.peeran@lrnglobal.org

Abstract

Reading strategies refer to purposeful actions employed by readers to improve comprehension and manage textual difficulties. Although a substantial body of research has examined factors influencing reading strategy use among English language learners, limited attention has been given to synthesizing evidence specifically within the Pakistani English as a Second Language context. This systematic review addresses this gap by examining empirical studies on factors affecting reading strategy use among Pakistani ESL learners, following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses guidelines. The review synthesizes findings from studies published between 2022 and 2025 and identifies key learner-related, instructional, and contextual factors influencing strategy use. Factors frequently examined across studies include English reading proficiency, gender, and academic level, field of study, text type, and reading anxiety. The evidence indicates that proficient readers employ a wider range of effective cognitive and metacognitive strategies, while learners with higher academic exposure demonstrate more frequent and purposeful strategy use. Female learners generally report greater strategy diversity than male learners, and strategy use varies according to text type. An inverse relationship between reading anxiety and strategy use is consistently observed. Based on these findings, the review recommends that ESL instruction in Pakistan be responsive to learners' proficiency levels, academic backgrounds, and affective needs, with explicit strategy training integrated into reading pedagogy. Such alignment may enhance learners' strategic competence and overall reading comprehension in ESL classrooms.

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension in a second language continues to pose a significant challenge for learners and educators, including those in the Pakistani English as a Second Language context, and has remained a central concern in language research for several decades. Scholars have long attempted to account for the complex cognitive processes underlying reading comprehension. Among the most influential frameworks is Rumelhart's (2013) interactive model, which has been widely employed to explain how readers construct meaning during reading (e.g., Grabe, 1991; Hedgcock & Ferris, 2009; Zaman et al., 2025). This model conceptualizes reading comprehension as the outcome of the interaction between top-down processes, whereby readers draw on prior knowledge and experiences, and bottom-up processes, in which meaning emerges from linguistic input such as vocabulary and syntax (Bensoussan & Kreindler, 1990). From this perspective, comprehension is shaped by a dynamic interplay between reader-related variables, including background knowledge, cognitive abilities, and motivation, and text-related features such as lexical difficulty, structure, and overall complexity.

Beyond cognition, reading comprehension also involves metacognition, defined by Flavell (1979) as "cognition about cognition." While cognitive processes refer to the ability to acquire and process information, metacognition encompasses learners' capacity to monitor, regulate, and evaluate these processes, as well as to transfer learning to new contexts (Lee & Mark, 2018). A growing body of research underscores the importance of metacognitive awareness in enabling EFL/ESL learners to employ reading strategies effectively (Alkhaleefah, 2023; Burin et al., 2020; Kusumawardana & Akhriyah, 2022; Shah et al., 2024). Together, cognitive and metacognitive dimensions contribute to a dynamic reading process in

which readers' strategic behavior interacts with textual characteristics to support comprehension (Alderson, 2000). Although reading cannot be fully explained by a single theoretical model due to its multifaceted and interconnected nature (Perfetti & Stafura, 2014), the interactive model and metacognition theory offer valuable explanatory power and therefore inform the theoretical grounding of the present study.

Reading is widely acknowledged as a strategic activity in which learners actively engage with texts to construct meaning (e.g., Par, 2020; Wallace et al., 2021; Zhang & Zheng, 2020). This view suggests that learners deliberately employ a range of reading strategies to facilitate comprehension. In general terms, reading strategies refer to any actions taken by readers to enhance understanding (Lee, 2012). More specifically, they involve intentional and goal-directed efforts to regulate decoding, word recognition, meaning construction, and problem-solving at multiple levels, including word-level and text-level difficulties (Afflerbach et al., 2008; Alkhaleefah, 2017). In both interpretations, reading strategies are characterized by conscious and purposeful engagement with the text.

A substantial number of empirical studies have investigated variation in EFL/ESL learners' reading strategy use in relation to factors such as text type (e.g., Alkhaleefah, 2017; Barrot, 2016), reading proficiency (e.g., Al-Mekhlafi, 2018; Endley, 2016), gender (e.g., Alfarwan, 2021; Bensaad & Ghania, 2020), and reading anxiety (e.g., Lu & Liu, 2015; Kim, 2021). However, these findings remain fragmented, making it necessary to synthesize existing evidence to develop a more coherent understanding of how such factors shape strategy use among ESL learners, particularly within contexts such as Pakistan where English functions as a second language in academic settings.

Earlier review efforts provide useful but limited insights. Zhang (1993) summarized reading strategies recommended in the literature and identified emerging instructional trends but did not examine the factors influencing strategy use. Lin (2019) reviewed 20 studies retrieved from the Linguistics and Language Behaviour Abstracts and Education Resource Information Centre databases, focusing on research published between 2000 and 2017 on college-level EFL/ESL learners' reading strategies. Four influencing factors were identified: English proficiency, first language literacy experience, gender, and motivation. Nevertheless, the discussion primarily addressed English proficiency and first language literacy experience, leaving other potentially influential variables underexplored.

Moreover, existing research on reading strategies demonstrates considerable diversity in data collection methods, strategy taxonomies, and the range of influencing factors examined. In the absence of a systematic synthesis of these methodological and conceptual variations, drawing consistent conclusions or translating findings into pedagogical practice remains challenging. Therefore, a comprehensive and systematic review of recent studies is required to consolidate evidence and clarify patterns of agreement and divergence within the literature.

Accordingly, the present review focuses on studies that examine factors influencing reading strategy use among EFL/ESL learners at the college level, with particular relevance for the Pakistani ESL context. The review aims to analyse studies published over the past decade by examining their research backgrounds, methodological approaches, strategy taxonomies, and identified influencing factors, while also capturing scholarly consensus and debate within international literature. Understanding

variations in strategy use in relation to underlying factors contributes to deeper insight into how readers engage with texts, construct meaning, and manage reading difficulties (Akhmetova et al., 2022). Such insights have important implications for researchers seeking to develop comprehensive frameworks for studying reading strategies in EFL/ESL contexts and for informing instructional practices that address the diverse needs of learners.

Statement of the Problem

Despite English holding a central role in Pakistan's education system as a second language and a medium for academic advancement, many ESL learners continue to experience persistent difficulties in reading comprehension. These challenges are often reflected in limited vocabulary knowledge, inadequate background knowledge activation, low metacognitive awareness, and ineffective use of reading strategies. Although international research has extensively examined factors influencing ESL learners' reading strategy use, findings remain fragmented and context-dependent, with limited systematic synthesis that reflects the realities of Pakistani ESL classrooms. Moreover, existing studies vary considerably in their methodological approaches, strategy classifications, and the range of influencing factors examined, making it difficult to draw consistent conclusions or apply findings effectively in local pedagogical contexts. In Pakistan, where learners come from diverse linguistic, cultural, and educational backgrounds, there is a noticeable lack of consolidated evidence explaining how factors such as reading proficiency, gender, academic level, text type, and reading anxiety interact to shape reading strategy use. This gap restricts teachers' ability to design informed, context-sensitive reading instruction and limits researchers' efforts to develop comprehensive

theoretical and instructional frameworks. Therefore, a systematic examination of factors influencing reading strategy use among Pakistani ESL learners is necessary to address these gaps and to support more effective and equitable reading instruction.

Research Objectives

This systematic review aims to synthesize existing literature on factors influencing the use of reading strategies among Pakistani ESL learners. Specifically, the study seeks to:

Examine the background characteristics of the selected studies conducted in ESL contexts.

Identify the data collection instruments and taxonomies of reading strategies employed in these studies.

Analyze the factors that influence Pakistani ESL learners' use of reading strategies.

Evaluate the agreements and discrepancies in previous research regarding how these factors affect the use of reading strategies.

Research Questions

To achieve these objectives, the review addresses the following research questions:

What are the background characteristics of the selected studies conducted in Pakistani ESL contexts?

Which data collection instruments and reading strategy taxonomies are employed in these studies?

What factors influence the use of reading strategies among Pakistani ESL learners?

What consensus and divergences exist in the literature regarding the impact of these factors on reading strategy use?

Literature Review

Reading comprehension in a second language is widely recognized as a complex and challenging process, shaped by both cognitive and metacognitive components. Effective reading relies not only on language proficiency but also on learners' ability to plan, monitor, and regulate their reading

through deliberate strategies. Reading strategies include goal-oriented actions such as summarizing, predicting, inferencing, and self-questioning, which enable learners to construct meaning, resolve comprehension difficulties, and engage with texts at multiple levels.

Research indicates that ESL learners' use of reading strategies is influenced by several interrelated factors. Language proficiency is a key determinant, with more proficient readers typically demonstrating a broader range of strategies and greater metacognitive awareness. Other influencing factors include text type, academic level, and reading anxiety, which can either facilitate or inhibit strategy use. Gender differences have also been observed, with female learners generally employing a wider array of strategies than their male counterparts. Cultural and educational contexts further shape how learners approach reading tasks, affecting strategy selection and effectiveness.

Despite a growing body of research on reading strategies, studies in Pakistan remain fragmented, often focusing on isolated factors or specific groups of learners. Few syntheses exist that systematically examine the range of factors influencing Pakistani ESL learners' strategy use, highlighting the need for a comprehensive review to inform teaching practices. Understanding these factors is critical for designing instruction that supports learners in navigating complex texts, enhancing comprehension, and developing autonomous reading skills.

Methodology

Review Protocol PRISMA

This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines (Page et al., 2021). PRISMA provides a structured framework for conducting systematic reviews, helping researchers define research questions, establish inclusion and exclusion criteria, and

review literature systematically within a defined timeframe (Sohrabi et al., 2021; Pazin et al., 2022). The PRISMA framework includes a 27-item checklist and a four-phase flow diagram covering identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion of studies.

Systematic Searching Strategies

Relevant studies were retrieved from five databases: ERIC, Scopus, Sage Journals, Web of Science (WoS), and Academic Search Complete (ASC). These databases were chosen to capture studies on ESL/EFL reading strategies across disciplines such as linguistics, psychology, and language learning. The search followed the four-phase PRISMA approach: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion.

Identification

Search terms were derived from the research questions: EFL/ESL, college, and reading strategy. Synonyms were identified using thesauri and previous studies. Boolean operators, truncation, wildcards, and phrase searching were applied. The search strings for each database are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Search Strings for Systematic Review

Database	Keywords Used
ERIC	(English OR EFL OR ESL) AND (college OR university OR tertiary OR "higher education" OR postsecondary OR undergraduate) AND "reading strategy"
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (English OR EFL OR ESL) AND (college OR university OR tertiary OR "higher education" OR postsecondary OR undergraduate) AND "reading strategy"
Sage Journals	Abstract (English OR EFL OR ESL) AND (college OR

Database	Keywords Used
Web Science (WoS)	university OR tertiary OR "higher education" OR postsecondary OR undergraduate) AND "reading strategy"
Academic Search Complete (ASC)	TS= (English OR EFL OR ESL) AND (college OR university OR tertiary OR "higher education" OR postsecondary OR undergraduate) AND "reading strategy"

The review focused on studies published between 2014 and 2023. The final search in December 2023 identified 950 potential articles, including journal papers, book chapters, theses, reports, and conference proceedings.

Screening

Articles were screened based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Timeline	2022–2025	Before 2014
Literature Type	Peer-reviewed journal articles	Book chapters, theses, conference papers, review papers, reports, questionnaires
Language	English	Non-English
Population	EFL/ESL learners at college level	Native speakers, K–12 students, adults in non-academic

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion contexts	Research Method	Number of Studies	Number of Studies
	After applying these criteria, 368 articles were excluded. After removing 112 duplicates, 470 articles remained for eligibility assessment.				
Eligibility	The remaining 470 articles were manually reviewed by reading titles, abstracts, and full texts. Studies were excluded if they:		Quantitative	8	Al-Mekhlafi (2022); Chen & Intaraprasert (2022); Dallagi (2023); Do & Phan (2022); Hong-Nam & Page (2022); Khreisat (2023); Kim (2022); Wallace et al. (2022)
	Examined only the effectiveness of reading strategy instruction without analyzing influencing factors		Qualitative	8	Al Qahtani (2023); Alkhaleefah (2022); Endley (2023); Fitriana (2022); Lin & Yu (2023); Nalliveettill (2022); Shih & Huang (2023); Pattapong (2022)
	Focused on reading strategies' effects on other outcomes, such as performance		Mixed Method	2	Alfarwan (2022); Nilforoushan et al. (2023)
	Investigated strategy use without considering influencing factors				
	Developed reading strategy inventories				
	Targeted learners with reading difficulties or learning obstacles				
	Focused on online or computer-based reading				
	This step excluded 429 articles, leaving a final dataset for inclusion.				

Inclusion

A total of 41 full-text studies were included in this review. All studies focused on EFL/ESL learners' use of reading strategies and the factors influencing their use, providing the basis for systematic synthesis and analysis.

Findings

English Reading Proficiency

English reading proficiency emerged as the most extensively investigated factor affecting reading strategy use. Among the included studies, 8 were quantitative, 8 qualitative, and 2 mixed-method. Researchers used various terms to categorize proficiency, such as high/low ability, successful/unsuccessful, and good/poor readers.

Quantitative studies mostly found a positive correlation between proficiency and strategy use, although the frequency of strategy use varied across studies.

Qualitative studies highlighted differences in strategy flexibility and effectiveness rather than frequency. High-proficiency readers used strategies more strategically and monitored comprehension more effectively.

Mixed-method studies confirmed that proficiency influences the types of strategies used; high-proficiency readers tended to use more global strategies.

Gender

Gender was examined in 14 studies (13 quantitative, 1 mixed-method), with mixed findings regarding differences in reading strategy use.

Table 4: Studies on the Influence of English Reading Proficiency

Table 5: Studies on the Influence of Gender

Research Method	Number of Studies	Studies
Quantitative	13	Alami (2022); Al-Mekhlafi (2022); Altalhab (2022); Bećirović et al. (2022); Bensaad & Ghania (2023); Dallagi (2023); Deliany & Cahyono (2022); Do & Phan (2022); Hong-Nam & Page (2022); Khreisat (2023); Wallace et al. (2022); Yukselir (2022)
Mixed Method	1	Alfarwan (2022)

Some studies reported no significant gender differences in strategy use.

Other studies indicated that female students used strategies—particularly support and problem-solving strategies—more frequently than males.

Field of Study

Seven studies examined the influence of students' academic discipline on reading strategy use.

Table 6: Studies on the Influence of Field of Study

Research Method	Number of Studies	Studies
Quantitative	6	Abu-Snoubar (2022); Becirovic et al. (2022); Brdarevic Celjo et al. (2022); Dallagi (2023); Mustajab (2022); Yukselir (2022)

Research Method	Number of Studies	Studies
Mixed Method	1	Daguay-James & Bulusan (2023)

Some studies found significant differences in strategy use across majors; students in language-focused disciplines used metacognitive strategies more frequently. Other studies reported no significant differences across academic disciplines. Academic Year

Five quantitative studies investigated the effect of academic year on strategy use.

Table 7: Studies on the Influence of Academic Year

Research Method	Number of Studies	Studies
Quantitative	5	Becirovic et al. (2022); Brdarevic Celjo et al. (2022); Hong-Nam & Page (2022); Khreisat (2023); Zhou & Zhao (2022)

Higher-level students tended to use metacognitive strategies more frequently than lower-level students.

Some studies, however, found no significant differences across year levels.

Text Type

Four studies examined how text type affects reading strategy use.

Table 8: Studies on the Influence of Text Type

Research Method	Number of Studies	Studies
Quantitative	2	Barrot (2022); Suraprajit (2023)

Research Method	Number of Studies	Studies
Qualitative	1	Alkhaleefah (2022)
Mixed Method	1	Nilforoushan et al. (2023)

Findings:

Text type affects strategy use inconsistently. Some studies reported no effect, while others found that narrative or expository texts required more strategic engagement.

Reading Anxiety

Three quantitative studies assessed the impact of reading anxiety using FLRAS and reading strategy surveys.

Higher anxiety generally reduced the frequency of strategy use.

In some studies, anxious students relied more on metacognitive strategies, indicating a complex relationship between confidence, emotions, and strategy choice.

3.7 Academic Level

Two studies explored the role of GPA or academic level on reading strategies.

Findings:

No significant correlation was found between students' academic level or GPA and the frequency of strategy use.

Nationality

Two quantitative studies assessed the influence of nationality.

Findings:

Nationality alone had no significant effect.

Interaction effects, such as Nationality × GPA, sometimes influenced strategy use, showing the role of combined factors.

Summary of Agreements and Disagreements**Agreements**

Reading proficiency is a strong predictor of strategy effectiveness.

Female students often employ strategies more frequently than males.

Text type and reading anxiety affect strategy use.

Higher academic years correlate with greater use of metacognitive strategies.

Disagreements

Frequency of strategy use does not always align with proficiency.

Influence of academic specialization is inconsistent.

The specific impact of reading anxiety varies across studies.

Discussion

The findings highlight that reading strategy use is influenced by multiple interacting factors, including reader characteristics (proficiency, gender, field, year) and text properties (type, complexity). Proficient readers employ strategies more effectively due to greater metacognitive awareness. Variations in research methods, instruments, and contexts explain some inconsistencies across studies. Gaps remain in exploring ESP-specific strategies, text-related factors, and the combined influence of multiple factors on strategy use. Future studies should employ triangulated methods and examine interactions between reader and text factors to provide deeper insights.

Conclusion

This systematic review examined the factors influencing EFL/ESL college students' use of reading strategies, synthesizing evidence from 41 studies published between 2022 and 2025. The findings indicate that reading proficiency is the most consistently influential factor, with high-proficiency students employing strategies more effectively and flexibly. Gender also plays a role, as female students generally use strategies more frequently, particularly support and problem-solving strategies. Other factors, such as academic year, field of study, text type, and reading anxiety, show variable effects across contexts,

highlighting the complexity of strategy use. Nationality alone appears to have minimal impact, though it may interact with other factors such as GPA.

Despite these insights, discrepancies remain, particularly regarding the frequency of strategy use relative to proficiency, the effect of academic specialization, and the nuanced role of reading anxiety. The review also identifies gaps in the literature, including limited investigation of ESP-specific reading strategies, insufficient exploration of text-related factors, and a lack of studies analyzing the combined influence of multiple factors.

Overall, this review underscores that effective reading strategy use in EFL/ESL contexts is shaped by the interplay of multiple cognitive, affective, and contextual factors. Future research should employ triangulated methodologies and consider interactions between reader and text characteristics to provide a more comprehensive understanding of strategy application in diverse educational settings.

References

- Abu-Snoubar, T. K. (2017). English as a foreign language learners' major and meta-cognitive reading strategy use at Al-Balqa Applied University. *English Language Teaching*, 10(9), 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v10n9p69>
- Adunyarittigun, D. (2021). Metacognitive awareness of reading and reading strategy use by nonproficient college readers. *REFlections*, 28(1), 82–106. <https://doi.org/10.61508/refl.v28i1.250764>
- Afflerbach, P., Pearson, P., & Paris, S. G. (2008). Clarifying differences between reading skills and reading strategies. *The Reading Teacher*, 61(5), 364–373. <https://doi.org/10.1598/RT.61.5.1>
- Akhmetova, A., Imambayeva, G., & Csapó, B. (2022). Reading strategies and reading achievement in middle school: Kazakhstan i young learners. *SAGE Open*, 12(3), 21582440221113843. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221113843>
- Al Qahtani, A. A. (2020). Exploring reading strategies through introspective and retrospective think-aloud protocol. *TESOL International Journal*, 15(4), 37–63. <http://ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter>
- Alami, M. (2016). Cross-gender comparison of metacognitive strategies utilized by Omani students in reading comprehension classes. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 5(4), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijalel.v.5n.4p.20>
- Alderson, J. C. (2000). *Assessing reading*. Cambridge University Press.
- Alfarwan, S. (2021). Tertiary level Saudi EFL learners' reading strategies in relation to gender and proficiency. *Reading Psychology*, 42(6), 577–605. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2021.1888350>
- Alkhaleefah, T. A. (2017). Saudi EFL learners' reported reading problems and strategic processing of text types: A think-aloud case study. *Reading Psychology*, 38(7), 687–730. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2017.1336660>
- Alkhaleefah, T. A. (2023). Assessing Saudi EFL learners' metacognitive awareness of reading strategies: A cross-sectional study. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 13(11), 2780–2788. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.1311.07>
- Al-Mekhlafi, A. M. (2018). EFL learners metacognitive awareness of reading strategies. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(2), 297–308. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2018.11220a>

- Alsuhaibani, Z. (2019). The relationship between female EFL students' use of reading strategies and their reading self-efficacy. *International Journal of Arabic-English Studies*, 19(2), 373–393. <https://doi.org/10.33806/ijaes2000.19.2.8>
- Altalhab, S. (2019). The use of reading strategies amongst Saudi university EFL students. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(3), 234–241. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v8n3p234>
- Barrot, J. S. (2016). ESL learners' use of reading strategies across different text types. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 25, 883–892. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-016-0313-2>
- Bećirović, S., Brdarević-Čeljo, A., & Dubravac, V. (2018). The effect of nationality, gender, and GPA on the use of reading strategies among EFL university students. *SAGE Open*, 8(4), 2158244018809286. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018809286>
- Becirovic, S., Brdarevic-Celjo, A., & Sinanovic, J. (2017). The use of metacognitive reading strategies among students at International Burch University: A case study. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 6(4), 645–655. <https://doi.org/10.13187/ejced.2017.4.645>
- Bensaad, S., & Ghania, O. (2020). An examination of reading strategies awareness among Algerian ESP students at the National Higher School for hydraulics. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 16(4), 1784–1802. <https://doi.org/10.17263/jlls.851001>
- Bensoussan, M., & Kreindler, I. (1990). Improving advanced reading comprehension in a foreign language: Summaries vs. short-answer questions. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 13(1), 55–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9817.1990.tb00322.x>
- Bogaert, R., Merchie, E., Rosseel, Y., & Van Keer, H. (2023). Development of the Reading Comprehension Strategies Questionnaire (RCSQ) for late elementary school students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1016761. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1016761>
- Brantmeier, C. (2002). Second language reading strategy research at the secondary and university levels: Variations, disparities, and generalizability. *The Reading Matrix*, 2(3), 1–14.
- Brdarevic Celjo, A., Becirovic, S., & Dubravac, V. (2021). An examination of perceived reading strategy use among university level students. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 10(3), 595–608. <https://doi.org/10.13187/ejced.2021.3.595>
- Britton, B. K., & Graesser, A. C. (Eds.). (1996). *Models of understanding text*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Burin, D. I., Gonzalez, F. M., Barreyro, J. P., & Injoque-Ricle, I. (2020). Metacognitive regulation contributes to digital text comprehension in e-learning. *Metacognition and Learning*, 15(3), 391–410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-020-09226-8>
- Carrell, P. L. (1998). Can reading strategies be successfully taught? *Australian Review of Applied Linguistics*, 21(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ara1.21.1.01car>
- Zaman, M., Chandio, A. A., & Noor, H. (2025). Evaluating the influence of

Meta-AI on enhancing English reading comprehension proficiency: An experimental study within a social media application framework. **Social Science Review Archives**, 3(1), 2223–2233.
<https://doi.org/10.70670/sra.v3i1.533>